

Solvent Extraction of Molybdenum(VI) with Malachite Green into Nitrobenzene

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A rapid and selective method has been developed for the extraction of Mo^{VI} with malachite green into nitrobenzene. The effects of various parameters on the extraction coefficient value, such as effect of pH, time of equilibration, solvents, effect of various anions and cations have been evaluated. The stoichiometry of metal to reagent determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction is found to be 1 : 1; it is further supported by the slope-ratio method.

Malachite green has been used for the solvent extraction of a large number of metal ions¹. However, the extraction of Mo^{VI} with this reagent for the radiochemical separation has not been reported. The present work describes a rapid and selective method for the extraction of Mo^{VI} with malachite green into nitrobenzene.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) reveal that maximum *E* value of 109 was obtained at pH 8.5 and a equilibration time of 6.0 min. The reproducibility of extraction was found to be 5.82%. The extraction of Mo^{VI} into different organic solvents was ascertained and nitrobenzene gave the maximum extraction coefficient value (Table 2).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH AND TIME OF EQUILIBRATION ON THE EXTRACTION COEFFICIENT VALUE OF Mo^{VI} WITH MALACHITE GREEN INTO NITROBENZENE

pH	% <i>E</i>	Time of equilibration min
2.0	75.00	6.0
3.0	81.80	6.0
4.0	90.90	6.0
5.0	97.72	6.0
6.0	98.38	6.0
7.0	98.95	6.0
8.0	98.95	6.0
8.5	99.09	6.0
8.5	99.03	6.0
8.5	99.02	6.0
8.5	98.97	6.0
9.0	98.96	6.0
10.0	97.91	6.0
10.5	94.73	6.0
8.5	98.00	3.0
8.5	98.59	4.0
8.5	98.73	5.0
8.5	99.09	6.0
8.5	98.97	7.0
8.5	98.90	8.0

Reproducibility = 5.82%.

The effect of metal ion concentration on the extraction of Mo^{VI} with malachite green into nitrobenzene was studied over the range 0.4–1.0 mg of Mo^{VI}. *E* value was found to increase with the increase in the concentration of metal ion.

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION COEFFICIENT VALUE OF Mo^{VI} WITH MALACHITE GREEN INTO DIFFERENT ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Solvent	<i>E</i>
Nitrobenzene	103.0
Isoamyl alcohol	18.0
Xylene	17.0
Chloroform	8.2
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	8.1
Heptanol	7.6
Isobutanol	6.6
1-Butanol	3.8
Nitromethane	3.2
Isobutyl methyl ketone	2.7
Cyclohexanone	1.0
Toluene	0.02
Amyl acetate	0.02
Benzene	0.02
Carbon tetrachloride	0.01
Cyclohexane	0.01
Heptane	0.004
Hexane	0.0015
Ethyl methyl ketone	0.0015

After equilibration, no phase separation was observed for *n*-propanol, pyridine and ethylene glycol.

The effect of various anions on the percentage extraction of Mo^{VI} revealed that the extraction was better than 99% when 100 mg each of sulphate, sulphide, bromate, chloride and fluoride, 50 mg each of thiosulphate, borate and oxalate, 10 mg each of bromide, hypophosphite, sulphide, cyanide, acetate and citrate were present. Iodide, nitrite, carbonate, EDTA, nitrate, perchlorate and bicarbonate interfered but their interference was removed by decomposing them with concentrated HNO₃ and HCl whereas the interference of nitrate was removed with con-

Fig 1 Reproducibility of substoichiometric extraction of Mo^{VI} with malachite green into nitrobenzene

centrated HCl. The interference of dichromate and chromate was suppressed by reducing it with HCl and H₂O₂ prior to the extraction of Mo^{VI}.

Of the elements studied, 1 mg each of Zn^{II}, Ba^{II}, Rb^I, Sc^{III}, Mn^{II}, Sn^{II}, Cl^I, Sb^{III}, Cs^I, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, S^{VI}, Se^{IV}, Sn^{IV}, Fe^{II}, Sb^V, Ce^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Cd^{II}, P^V, Eu^{III} and In^{III} were extracted to the extent of less than 1.0%. Cr^{III}, Tl^I, Ru^{III}, La^{III} and Ir^{IV} were extracted between 1.0 and 10.0%. Fe^{III} which was extracted to greater than 16%, was suppressed by reducing it with 2 ml of hydrazine hydrate. Zr^{IV} which was extracted to above 69%, was masked with 25 mg of tartrate. Ag^I was extracted to greater than 82% but it was removed by precipitating as AgCl. The interference of Cr^{VI} which was extracted to above 89%, was decreased by reducing Cr^{VI} to Cr^{III} with HCl and H₂O₂. W^{VI} was extracted to greater than 91% and was removed by precipitating as tungstic acid prior to the extraction of Mo^{VI}. Tc^{VII} (tracer level) and Hg^{II} were extracted to greater than 97%, but their interference was suppressed by reducing Tc^{VII} with 100 mg of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and that of Hg^{II} as mercury metal with freshly prepared SnCl₂ solution.

The stoichiometry of the extracted species determined by the method of substoichiometric extraction was carried out as follows. In a series of separatory funnels, increasing amount of Mo^{VI} labelled with ⁹⁹Mo, was added water (5 ml) containing malachite green (19.32 mg). The volume of the solution was made up to 15 ml with distilled water after adjusting the pH of the solution. The aqueous phase was equilibrated for 6.0 min with nitrobenzene (15 ml). The phases were allowed to separate. A 2-ml aliquot of the organic phase was taken for counting on a G.M. counter using aluminium absorber (13.4 mg cm⁻²). The activity, i.e. counts per 50 s of 2-ml aliquot of the organic phase was plotted against the amount of Mo^{VI} taken. From Fig. 1, it can be seen that activity increased with an increasing concentration of Mo^{VI}, till it was subequivalent to the reagent added. After reaching the equivalence point, corresponding to metal : reagent ratio of 1 : 1, the activity remained con-

stant with an increase in the concentration of Mo^{VI}. A break was observed at the equivalence point corresponding to metal : reagent ratio of 1 : 1. This was further supported by the slope-ratio method.

Decontamination factor for different elements was determined at substoichiometric level and was found to be greater than 10⁵ for most elements.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. grade. ⁹⁹Mo (67 h) and isotopes used were supplied by BRIT, Bombay. The stock solution of Mo^{VI} was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of molybdic acid in a minimum amount of ammonia and then diluted with distilled water. Solutions of anions were prepared by dissolving appropriate salts in distilled water and that of cations were prepared in the same way, but 5 ml of concentrated HCl was added to the solution wherever required. The strength of these solutions was determined by the standard method². The solution of reagent malachite green oxalate (Loba Chem) was prepared in distilled water. The purity of reagent was checked by determining its m.p. (164°).

Gamma-emitters were counted on a single-channel pulse-height analyser in conjunction with a 3.5 cm × 3.5 cm NaI(Tl) well-type crystal detector. Beta-emitters were counted on a thin end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, high voltage and a timer.

Extraction procedure : To Mo^{VI} (1.0 mg) labelled with ⁹⁹Mo was added 1% aqueous solution (5 ml) of malachite green. The volume of the solution was made up to 15 ml after adjusting the pH of the solution with HCl or ammonia. The mixture was equilibrated for 6 min with nitrobenzene (15 ml). The phases were allowed to separate and a 2-ml aliquot of each phase was taken in a planchet, evaporated to dryness and taken for counting on a G.M. counter using 13.4 mg cm⁻² aluminium absorber to cut off the soft conversion electrons of ^{99m}Tc. The extraction coefficient value *E* was calculated using the equation :

$$E = \frac{\text{Activity of 2 ml aliquot of the organic phase}}{\text{Activity of 2 ml aliquot of the aqueous phase}}$$

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